

**MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PARTICULATE REINFORCED COMPOSITES PREDICTED
USING FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS AND SPATIAL STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES**

F. J. Guild
Department of Materials,
Queen Mary College,
Mile End Road,
London E1 4NS, UK.

P. J. Davy
School of Mathematics,
University of Bath,
Claverton Down,
Bath BA2 7AY, UK.

and

R. J. Young
Department of Polymer Science and Technology,
UMIST,
P.O. Box 88,
Manchester M60 1QD, UK.

ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of a predictive model describing the mechanical properties of particulate reinforced composites using a combination of finite element analysis and spatial statistical techniques. The statistical analysis allows results from finite element analysis to be applied to real composite materials. The model is applied to epoxy resin reinforced with hard glass spheres and soft rubber spheres. Excellent agreement is found between predicted values of stiffness and experimental values. Preliminary results describing stress distribution in epoxy resin reinforced with the two types of particle are presented.

INTRODUCTION

Particulate reinforcement of polymers is used widely to increase their strength and stiffness whilst also reducing their cost. The development of a predictive model describing the properties of these composite materials will lead to understanding and interpretation of their static and fracture properties, and to useful, logical, design of new materials.

Finite element analysis has opened the possibility of the development of such a predictive model. Finite element analysis is a very powerful technique; results from a finite element grid include predictions of values of stiffness and detailed stress distributions. There exists, however, a major problem in the application of finite element analysis to composite materials, namely the association between the finite element model and the

real material. We have achieved this link by the combination of finite element analysis and statistics.

The composite material is modelled by a collection of cylinders of random radius equal to half-height, each containing a single filler sphere of constant radius. The average volume of the cylinders is the same as if the cylinders filled space, and the variability in cylinder volume is determined by the distribution of distances within space-filling Voronoi cells. The positions of the spheres are governed by the so-called Gibbs hard-core model, which allows complete randomness apart from the constraint that no two spheres may overlap. Properties of a large volume of material can be determined by averaging stress and strain over the collection of cylinders with a weighting proportional to volume.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

For any arrangement of spheres of constant radius within a matrix, a natural subdivision of the material into space-filling cells is provided by the Voronoi tessellation, in which each point is assigned to the cell containing its nearest sphere centre. Voronoi cells are in general too irregular to use as a basis for finite element analysis, but statistical information about them can be used to construct a collection of random cylindrical cells which mimic the microstructure of the material.

Let λ denote the mean number of sphere centres per unit volume, p denote the volume fraction occupied by the spheres and r denote the sphere radius. These three quantities are related by the equation

$$p = 4\pi \lambda r^3 / 3 \quad (1)$$

Let X be the distance from a sphere centre to the boundary of its Voronoi cell in a randomly chosen direction. If \bar{E} denotes expected or mean value, averaged over all directions and all spheres, the space-filling property of Voronoi cells can be expressed as

$$\bar{E} (4\pi X^3 / 3) = \lambda^{-1} \quad , \quad \text{i.e.} \quad \bar{E}(X^3 / r^3) = p^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Although the mean value of X^3 / r^3 depends only upon volume fraction, the variability of X/r depends also upon the actual arrangement of spheres, tending to be smaller for more regular structures and larger for clustered structures.

One useful model for random arrangements of spheres is the Gibbs hard-core model, for which all non-overlapping configurations are equally

likely [1]. For this model, a close approximation to the distribution function of X/r is given by (see [2])

$$F(y) = 1 - \exp\{-\kappa(y^3 + 3y^{-1} - 4)\} \quad (y \geq 1) \quad (3)$$

where κ is computed numerically to ensure that (2) is satisfied, i.e.

$$\int_0^1 x^{-2} \exp\{-\kappa(x^{-1} + 3x^{1/3} - 4)\} dx = (1-p)/p \quad (4)$$

Figure 1 shows the probability density function of X corresponding to (3) for $\lambda=1$ and various values of p . Changing λ will merely change the scales on the two axes. Note that as p increases, the mode (position of peak density) remains almost the same, while the spread becomes much narrower, indicating that the structure becomes more regular at higher volume fractions.

Figure 1: Probability density function g_x , of half interparticle distant X for $\lambda=1$ and volume fraction p ranging from 0 to 0.3.

Figure 2: Constraint upon angle θ between direction and horizontal plane in order that distance from centre boundary of cylinder should exceed Z .

The distance Z from the centre of a cylinder to its boundary in a random direction is $R \sec \theta$, where R is the radius, equal to half height, of the cylinder and θ is the angle between the base of the cylinder and the chosen direction, as shown in Figure 2. Averaging over all spatial directions, which entails a density of $\cos \theta$ for θ , we obtain

$$\bar{E}(Z^m) = R^m \int_0^{\pi/4} \sec^{m-1} \theta (1 + \tan \theta) d\theta \quad (5)$$

By allowing R to be random, it is possible to match the moments of Z and X . Using (2), (3) and (5) we obtain

$$\bar{E} (R^3/r^3) = 2/3p = R_p^3/r^3 \quad (6)$$

and

$$\overline{CV} (R^3/r^3) = (1.1108)^{-1} p^2 \bar{E}(X^6/r^6) - 1 \quad (7)$$

where

$$\bar{E} (X^6/r^6) = 1 + 2 \int_0^1 x^{-3} \exp[-\kappa(x^{-1} + 3x^{1/3} - 4)] dx \quad (8)$$

The notation R_p denotes the cylinder radius achieving an internal volume fraction of p for a sphere of radius r contained within it, which is used for the primary finite element grid at this volume fraction. \overline{CV} denotes coefficient of variation, i.e. variance divided by squared mean. The equations (6)–(8) have been expressed in terms of ratios of the form R/r as the properties to be investigated depend only upon this ratio and not upon the actual units of length which are adopted. Table 1 lists values of κ , R_p/r and $\overline{CV} (R^3/r^3)$ for various values of volume fraction.

TABLE 1

Parameter κ of interparticle distance distribution (found numerically from (4), primary grid ratio R_p/r and coefficient of variation of R^3/r^3) for volume fraction p ranging from .05 to .4.

p	κ	R_p/r	$\overline{CV} (R^3/r^3)$
.05	.0578	2.3713	.5966
.1	.1319	1.8821	.4651
.2	.3446	1.4938	.2763
.3	.6894	1.3050	.1494
.4	1.2694	1.1856	.0612

Having approximated the composite material by a collection of random cylinders, there remains the problem of relating its global properties to individual cell properties. In order to average stress and strain over a large volume of material, each component cylinder must be weighted according to its volume, which is equivalent to weighting according to R^3 . Let E_T be Young's modulus of the total material to which a vertical

load is applied, σ_T be a local stress at a point, and let P and E denote the load and Young's modulus of a cylindrical cell within the material. It will be assumed that the load on each cell is parallel to the axis of the cylinder. The local stress σ within a cylinder of radius R is calculated by assuming unit average stress applied to the cylinder. Therefore, when averaging over the combined material we must weight according to the allocated load per unit area $P/\pi R^2$ in addition to the volume weighting of R^3 . Then

$$E_T = \text{average stress} / \text{average vertical strain} = \bar{E} (R^3 P / \pi R^2) / \bar{E} (R^3 P / \pi R^2 E) \\ = \bar{E} (RP) / E (RP/E) \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_T = \bar{E} (R^3 \sigma \cdot P / \pi R^2) / \bar{E} (R^3 \cdot P / \pi R^2) = \bar{E} (RP\sigma) / \bar{E} (RP) \quad (10)$$

The allocation of loads within a real material is complex, but useful bounds for E_T and σ_T can be obtained by assuming constant stress (P proportional to R^2 , denoted by superscript (1)) and constant vertical strain (P proportional to $R^2 E$, denoted by superscript (2)). Substituting for P in (1) and (11), and using (6),

$$E_T^{(1)} = R^3 / \bar{E} (R^3 / E) \approx \{E_p^{-1} + d(E^{-1})\}^{-1} \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_T^{(1)} = \bar{E} (R^3 \sigma) / R_p^3 \approx \sigma_p + d(\sigma) \quad (12)$$

$$E_T^{(2)} = \bar{E} (R^3 E) / R_p^3 \approx E_p + d(E) \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_T^{(2)} = \bar{E} (R^3 \sigma E) / \bar{E} (R^3 E) \approx \{\sigma_p E_p + d(\sigma E)\} / E_T^{(2)} \quad (14)$$

where E_p and σ_p denote the values of E and σ calculated for the primary finite element grid for ratio R_p/r , and for any property function f , $d(f)$ is calculated from the formula

$$d(f) = \frac{1}{2} (R_p^3 / r^3) (R^3 f / r^3)'' \bar{CV} (R^3 / r^3) \quad (15)$$

The double prime appearing in (15) denotes the second derivative with respect to R^3/r^3 . The approximations in (11)–(14) are derived by using second-order Taylor's series expansions about R_p^3/r^3 before evaluating expected values. We shall refer to d as a dispersion factor, which is needed to adjust the primary grid property according to the type of dispersion of the spheres within the matrix. If R^3f/r^3 were exactly linear in (R^3/r^3) , the dispersion factor $d(f)$ would be zero, as the contributions from cylinders smaller than average would exactly balance the contributions from larger cylinders. In the non-linear case, however, irregularities in microstructure as reflected in $\overline{CV}(R^3/r^3)$ cause the properties of the total material to differ from those of the representative cell having ratio R_p/r .

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The development of the finite element model is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Development of the Finite Element Model

Analysis is carried out for a sphere, radius r , centred in a cylinder of resin, half-height equal to radius, R . The cylinder may be represented by the plane ABCD using axi-symmetric elements, the y -axis being the axis of symmetry. A typical finite element grid is shown in Figure 4;

Figure 4 The Finite Element Model:

(a) Typical Grid

(b) Comparison of original (—) and deflected (...) grids

load is applied via prescribed displacements of the nodes along CD. Constraints are applied such that BC remains parallel to its original direction, and AB and DA remain stationary, as shown in Figure 4.

The finite element package used is LUSAS, running on an ICL 2988 computer. Results from LUSAS include reactions to earth for the nodes along the free edges, for the one radian segment analysed. Thus the average stress applied to the cylinder can be calculated. Young's modulus, E , is found from this average stress and the strain applied via the prescribed displacements. The results include stresses in three dimensions at each node point. Stress results may be presented as contour diagrams. Post-processing of results transforms the stresses around the interface to polar coordinates, as indicated in Figure 3. All stresses are presented here as stress concentration factors, that is the ratio of that stress to the average stress applied.

Finite element analysis is thus capable of very useful description of the properties of composite materials for the grid analysed; the difficulty lies in the application of the results to real materials with complex arrangement of reinforcement. We have achieved the link between results from the finite element grid and real composite materials by the development of statistical analysis described above. The implementation of

that analysis has been fully described elsewhere [2], and will be briefly summarised here.

The volume fraction of spheres, p , is related to the radius ratio of the finite element grid, the primary grid, via the simple calculation of the volume fraction of sphere within that cylinder. However the property values found for that grid must be processed before they can be related to that volume fraction, p . All results are presented as "equal stress" (subscript (1)) and "equal strain" (subscript (2)) bounds arising from the assumption made regarding the distribution of load to the cylinders. The results presented here are values of Young's modulus, E , and concentration of applied stress, σ_{yy} . The property value is used to calculate the appropriate property function, f , via:

$$\text{equal stress: } E: f = 1/E \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma: f = E \quad (18)$$

$$\text{equal strain: } E: f = E \quad (19)$$

$$\sigma: f = E \cdot \sigma \quad (20)$$

The dispersion factor $d(f)$ for the property function f is calculated using equation 15. The second differential is found from finite element results from grids with slightly larger and slightly smaller radius ratios. The coefficient of variation factor, $\overline{CV}(R^3/r^3)$, is calculated from equations 7 and 8, where κ is defined in equation 4. The dispersion factor is added to the value of the property function and the true property value for volume fraction p can be calculated.

RESULTS

Theoretical predictions for the variation of Young's modulus with volume fraction for hard, glass particles and soft, rubber particles are shown in Figure 5. The theoretical predictions for the glass particles are compared with careful experimental measurements from the literature [3]; the agreement is excellent throughout the range of volume fraction. Constituent material properties for the rubber-reinforced material are more uncertain than those for the glass-reinforced material; these predictions have been made assuming perfect separation between the phases. We note that the near linear relationship between volume fraction and modulus is of the same form as that measured experimentally, and that the magnitude of decrease, namely around 30% for 20% rubber volume fraction, is the same as that measured experimentally [4].

(a)

Predictions ● $E_T^{(1)}$ (equal stress)
 ○ $E_T^{(2)}$ (equal strain)
 X Expt. values with error bars

(b)

Predictions ● $E_T^{(1)}$ (equal stress)
 ○ $E_T^{(2)}$ (equal strain)

Figure 5 Variation of Young's modulus, E , with volume fraction of spheres
 (a) Glass spheres and comparison with experimental values [3]
 (b) Rubber spheres

Stress distributions in glass-reinforced resin are shown in Figure 6;

(a)

M resin matrix; G glass sphere; r radial stress;
 t tangential stress; s shear stress

(b)

Figure 6 Stress distributions in resin-reinforced with 21.1% volume fraction glass spheres

(a) Stresses around interface, in polar coordinates (Fig. 3).
 (b) Contours of stress concentration factor of applied stress, σ_{yy} .

these results are not numerically exact since they have not been processed, but points of interest may be found. The results in Figure 6a show that the radial and shear stresses on either side of the interface are identical as required; this is a stringent test for the finite element grid. Radial stress passes through zero at angle, θ , = 68; this point remains constant for all volume fractions. This prediction is in agreement with experimental results and other theoretical predictions [5]. Maximum stress concentration is in the resin just above the pole of the sphere; this position is that found experimentally and by other theoretical predictions [6]. The magnitude of this stress concentration factor increases with increasing volume fraction of glass spheres from 1.98 at 5.7% to 3.07 at 49.2%. There is a concentration of shear stress at the interface, about midway between the pole and equator of the sphere. The absolute magnitude of this stress concentration factor decreases with increasing volume fraction; for the range of volume fraction shown in Figure 6 the value changes from -1.02 to -0.69. The values quoted are for the equal stress bound; the equal strain bound is less than 1% greater for all values.

The different relationships between stress concentration factor and volume fraction indicate change in fracture behaviour at different volume fractions. The implications of these results are fully discussed elsewhere [7].

Stress distributions for the resin reinforced with rubber spheres are less complicated. Maximum stress concentration for applied stress occurs at the equator of the sphere; this position is that found experimentally and by other theoretical predictions [6]. There is negligible transmission of applied stress to the rubber sphere, and no shear stress concentration at the interface. Values of the stress concentration factor of applied stress are considerably higher than those for the resin reinforced with glass spheres; the values increase with increasing volume fraction. For the range of volume fraction shown in Figure 6, the stress concentration of applied stress ranges from 2.13 to 5.74. The values quoted are for the equal stress bound; values for the equal strain bound are all between 1% and 2% lower.

The predictions of stress distributions for epoxy resin reinforced with rubber spheres show no change in fracture site over the range of volume fraction; however the very high values of stress concentration factor at high volume fractions could indicate a change in fracture behaviour. Experimental results indicate that fracture behaviour of

rubber-reinforced resin may be described by the presence of an "incipient flaw" [6]; these theoretical predictions support this explanation. We note that these results for resin reinforced with soft particles may be useful in the description of the failure of resin reinforced with glass spheres; the yielded region would behave as a soft particle. These implications are fully discussed elsewhere [7].

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Results from finite element analysis can provide valuable insights into the behaviour of composite materials. Our combination of spatial statistical techniques and finite element analysis allows the application of finite element analysis to real composite materials, leading to most useful results.

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